

**Machine Learning and Big Data in
Health Care (ML@HC) Special Session**

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In the present era, Machine Learning (ML) has been extensively used for many applications to real world problems. ML techniques are very suitable for Big Data Mining, to extract new knowledge and build predictive models that given a new input can provide in the output a reliable estimate. On the other hand, healthcare is one of the fastest growing data segments of the digital world, with healthcare data increasing at a rate of about 50 % per year. There are three primary sources of big data in healthcare: providers and payers (including EMR, imaging, insurance claims and pharmacy data), -omic data (including genomic, epigenomic, proteomic, and metabolomic data), and patients and non-providers (including data from smart phone and Internet activities sensors and monitoring tools).

The growth of big data in oncology, as well as other severe diseases (such as Alzheimer's Disease, etc.) can provide unprecedented opportunities to explore the biopsychosocial characteristics of these diseases and for descriptive observation, hypothesis generation, and prediction for clinical, research and business issues. The results of big data analysis can be incorporated into standards and guidelines and will directly impact clinical decision making. Oncologists and professionals from related medical fields can increasingly evaluate the results from research studies and commercial analytical products that are based on big data, using ML techniques. Furthermore, all these applications can be Web-based, so are very useful for the post treatment of the patients.

The aim of this special session was to serve as an interdisciplinary forum for bringing together specialists from the scientific areas of Computer & Web Engineering, Data Science, Semantic Computing, Bioinformatics-Personalized Medicine, clinicians and caregivers. The focus of this special session is on current technological advances and challenges about the development of big data-driven algorithms, methods and tools; furthermore, to investigate how ML-aware applications can contribute towards Big Data analysis on post treatment follow up.

The stimulus to this scientific forum was the presentation of the ONCORELIEF project (H2020-GA No. 875392): *A Smart Digital Guardian Angel Enhancing Cancer Patient Wellbeing and Health Status Improvement Following Treatment*. ONCORELIEF aims to deliver a framework that consists of three main sub-systems: 1) a *back-end data platform* where data are securely collected from heterogeneous sources, anonymized, annotated and stored, etc., 2) an Artificial Intelligence (AI) *engine* built on top of the back-end platform, which consumes and analyses data, extracts important features, produces meaningful AI models and updates them accordingly, produces correlations, etc.) a *downloadable application (ONCORELIEF Guardian Angel)* available for portable devices, which will be connected with the ONCORELIEF platform and with patients' sensing devices. It runs locally and uses models produced by the AI engine to extract insights on the patient life and condition and make suggestions. The GA may optionally send data back both for research-related reasons (another source of big data) and for computation offloading reasons (AI engine not

powerful enough on the mobile phone). These models are then downloaded to personal, portable devices in order to locally analyze individual data and to generate *QoL* (*Quality of Life*) indices, recommendations and warnings for the patients using the application. The application has been implemented and a pilot phase is running. The first results, with real data obtained from cancer patients, were reported and they are very promising.

Furthermore, a variety of Machine Learning methods have been presented insight the special session, such as explainable interactive image classification and deep learning techniques in order to train predictive models, using big data. Finally, these methods have been used for medical image classification, big -omics data analysis, supportive recommendations to cancer patients, neurological disorder patients and dementia risk prediction.

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**Machine Learning and Big Data
in Health Care (ML@HC)
(Invited SPEECH)**

Smart Digital Guardian Angel Enhancing Cancer Patient Wellbeing and Health Status Improvement Following Treatment

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Abstract. ONCORELIEF aims to deliver a framework that consists of three main sub-systems: 1) a **back-end data platform** where data are securely collected from heterogeneous sources, anonymised, annotated and stored, etc., 2) an **AI engine** built on top of the back-end platform, which consumes and analyses data, extracts important features, produces meaningful AI models and updates them accordingly, produces correlations, etc., 3) a **downloadable application (ONCORELIEF Guardian Angel)** available for portable devices, which will be connected with the ONCORELIEF platform and with patients' sensing devices. It runs locally and uses models produced by the AI engine to extract insights on the patient life and condition and make suggestions. The GA may optionally send data back both for research-related reasons (another source of big data) and for computation offloading reasons (AI engine not powerful enough on the mobile phone). These models are then downloaded to personal, portable devices in order to locally analyze individual data and to generate **QoL (Quality of Life) indices**, recommendations and warnings for the patients using the application. The application has been implemented and a pilot phase is running. The first results, with real data obtained from cancer patients, were reported and they are very promising.